

The Effects of Teaching AI and Robotics for High School Students: A Case Study in Uzbekistan

Javlonbek Abdusalilov, Head of Division, Republican scientific and methodological Center for the development of Education Tashkent, Uzbekistan, javlontuit@gmail.com, +998 998032912

Doniyorbek Ahmadaliev, Head of Division, Republican scientific and methodological Center for the development of Education Tashkent, Uzbekistan, ilmiyor@outlook.com, +998 998749103

Ryum-Duck Oh, Professor, Department of Software & IT Convergence Korea National University of Transportation Chungju, South Korea rdoh@ut.ac.kr, +82 10 5015 5269

Abstract— This research explores the effects of teaching artificial intelligence (AI) and robotics to high school students in Uzbekistan, particularly in the context of secondary education. The study assesses students' and parents' perceptions, the challenges faced in delivering AI and robotics education, and the outcomes of a summer school program that introduced these technologies. Findings suggest that AI and robotics education enhances students' critical thinking, collaboration, and problem-solving skills while generating a strong interest in STEM fields.

Keywords—Artificial Intelligence (AI), Robotics, STEM education, High school education, Informatics classes, Computational thinking, Fourth Industrial Revolution.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence and robotics are rapidly shaping the future workforce, and incorporating these topics into high school Informatics and Information Technologies (Informatics’) education program has become crucial. In Uzbekistan, the push to modernize education aligns with global trends emphasizing AI and robotics in preparing students for future careers in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics). This research evaluates the effects of introducing AI and robotics in secondary education, particularly in Informatics’ classes.

The Fourth Industrial Revolution is transforming job markets, and the skill sets required for future careers. World Economic Forum [1] reports that AI, machine learning, and robotics are among the top skills needed in the future. As a result, early exposure to these topics can help prepare students for the workforce by fostering digital literacy, computational thinking, and problem-solving abilities.

In 2024, a training program on AI and robotics was conducted at School No. 129 in Tashkent, Uzbekistan, in collaboration with the Korea National University of Transportation. The training aimed to provide hands-on experience in AI and robotics for high school students and their teachers. The program included practical projects using AI tools, robotics equipment, and problem-solving sessions.

For our research we have identified following research questions:

1. How does teaching AI and robotics affect students’ perceptions of STEM subjects?
2. What impact does AI and robotics education have on students’ problem-solving and critical thinking skills?
3. What are the challenges faced in delivering AI and robotics education in secondary schools?

Literature Review

The integration of AI and robotics into high school education has gained global attention as an effective means to foster computational thinking, creativity, and problem-solving skills. Studies by Benitti [2] and Grover & Pea [3] highlight that teaching robotics enhances students' engagement and technical abilities in STEM fields. Moreover, Wing [4] emphasizes the importance of computational thinking, a core component of AI and robotics education.

Project-Based Learning (PBL) has proven to be an effective strategy for teaching AI and robotics, as it allows students to engage in hands-on activities and solve real-world problems. In AI and robotics education, students design, build, and program robots to complete specific tasks, which enhances their understanding of programming, electronics, and mechanical systems. Recent research by Lin [5] found that PBL-based AI and robotics lessons improved students' problem-solving skills and fostered creativity. Students who participated in these lessons demonstrated a higher level of engagement and motivation compared to traditional teaching methods.

Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL) encourages students to ask questions, explore problems, and discover solutions on their own or with minimal guidance. IBL pushes students to think critically, make hypotheses, and test their ideas through experimentation and iteration. A study by Ali [6] on teaching robotics using Inquiry-Based Learning found that students showed significant improvements in their analytical thinking and practical skills. Moreover, students reported increased satisfaction and confidence in their ability to understand and apply AI concepts.

Collaborative learning, where students work together to complete projects or solve problems, is another effective approach in teaching AI and robotics. In the context of AI and robotics, students can collaborate on designing algorithms, building robots, or programming solutions, thereby gaining hands-on experience and learning from each other. Hao and Liu [7] explored collaborative learning in AI education and found that students working in teams were more engaged and produced higher-quality projects. The collaborative environment helped students develop interpersonal skills and encouraged peer-to-peer learning.

Benefits of Teaching AI and Robotics in High School

Teaching AI and robotics in high school offers numerous benefits that extend beyond academic performance. These topics help students build valuable skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, creativity, and digital literacy.

3.1. Enhancing STEM Engagement

Integrating AI and robotics into the Informatics' education program increases student interest in STEM subjects. Benitti [8] found that robotics education significantly enhances students' engagement and motivation in STEM fields. The hands-on nature of AI and robotics allows students to apply theoretical concepts in practical settings, making the learning experience more dynamic and engaging.

Kim et al. [9] conducted a study on the impact of robotics education on high school students and found that 85% of students expressed a greater interest in pursuing STEM-related careers after participating in robotics classes. This suggests that exposure to AI and robotics can play a crucial role in shaping students' future career choices.

3.2. Developing Computational Thinking and Problem-Solving Skills

AI and robotics education fosters computational thinking, which is essential for problem-solving in a technology-driven world. Grover and Pea [3] argue that computational thinking helps students develop algorithmic thinking, abstraction, and logical reasoning. These skills are particularly important in AI and robotics, where students need to create and optimize algorithms to solve complex problems.

A study by Lye and Koh [10] on computational thinking in high school students revealed that students who were exposed to robotics and AI showed marked improvements in their ability to break down complex problems and develop solutions.

3.3. Encouraging Creativity and Innovation

Robotics and AI projects encourage students to think creatively and explore innovative solutions to real-world problems. Papert [11] emphasized that students learn best when they are actively engaged in creating something tangible. In robotics

education, students have the opportunity to design, build, and program robots, which fosters creativity and innovation.

Gura [12] found that robotics projects provide students with a platform to express their creativity while learning important technical skills. By integrating AI and robotics into the Informatics' education program, schools can nurture a generation of innovative thinkers who are equipped to tackle future challenges.

Challenges in Teaching AI and Robotics

While the benefits of teaching AI and robotics are well-documented, there are several challenges to successfully implementing these topics in high school Informatics' education program.

4.1. Lack of Teacher Training

One of the main challenges in teaching AI and robotics is the lack of trained teachers. Many teachers may not have the necessary expertise to effectively teach these complex topics. A survey by Khan [13] found that only 40% of teachers felt confident in their ability to teach AI and robotics. This highlights the need for comprehensive teacher training programs to equip educators with the skills and knowledge needed to teach these topics effectively.

4.2. Resource Constraints

Implementing AI and robotics education requires significant resources, including access to robotics kits, AI software, and technological infrastructure. Benitti [2] noted that resource constraints are a significant barrier for schools, particularly in low-income areas. Schools may lack the funds to purchase robotics kits or provide students with access to the necessary technology, limiting the reach of AI and robotics education.

4.3. Integration AI and robotics into Informatics' education program

Integrating AI and robotics into existing Informatics' education program can be challenging due to time constraints and the need to balance new content with traditional subjects. The interdisciplinary approaches, where AI and robotics are integrated into math, science, and technology classes, may help overcome this

challenge. However, redesigning Informatics' education program requires careful planning and collaboration among Informatics teachers and educators.

Methodology and Results

For measuring the perception of teaching and learning of AI and S/W in secondary education in Uzbekistan we chose to take a survey with four groups of participants. They are high school students (10th and 11th grade school students) of 129-school in Tashkent, their parents, ICT teachers and school principals are invited to participate. The positive response for the survey invitation was as follows: 96 students and 116 parents; 2 ICT teachers, and 2 School principals. During the questionnaire visit to the school 1 group of students was missing because they had finished class and went home at that time, that's why the number of parents is more than students in the response number. We invited more parents than students to participate in the survey to see their interest in teaching AI and SW for their children. A mixed-methods approach was used, combining surveys and post-training interviews to gather qualitative and quantitative data. Two types of survey items were designed to assess:

- Education status: The current level of AI and software (S/W) programming knowledge among students, teachers, and school staff.
- Necessity of educational support: The need for tailored educational resources to improve AI and robotics teaching.

Surveys were distributed to students, parents, teachers, and school principals. Additionally, a post-training survey was conducted to evaluate the outcomes of the AI and robotics summer school program.

Responses were coded and analyzed to identify trends in perceptions, engagement, and learning outcomes. Statistical analysis was performed to compare the pre- and post-training results, and qualitative feedback was categorized to highlight key themes.

Out of 96 students surveyed, 93% reported an increased interest in learning AI and robotics after the summer school program. Approximately 60% expressed a

desire to further their studies in AI and robotics, with a strong interest in applying their knowledge to automation and problem-solving tasks.

Students who participated in the AI and robotics training demonstrated a marked increase in engagement. The majority of students enjoyed hands-on projects and collaborative activities, which enhanced their understanding of AI and its real-world applications.

Students who engaged in robotics projects showed improved problem-solving abilities and critical thinking. 85% of students agreed that working on AI and robotics enhanced their ability to analyze and solve complex problems. 81% of students indicated that they would like to participate in future AI and robotics programs.

Teachers and parents overwhelmingly supported the introduction of AI and robotics into the Informatics' education program. The surveys also revealed that while parents were generally satisfied with the educational process, many expressed concerns about the availability of adequate resources and teacher training.

The main challenges identified were:

- Resource limitations: Limited access to robotics kits and AI tools in schools hindered the expansion of these programs.
- Teacher training: ICT teachers expressed the need for more comprehensive training in AI and robotics to effectively teach these topics.

Discussion

The results of this study align with global research that demonstrates the benefits of integrating AI and robotics into secondary education. As noted by Kim [9], students who are exposed to AI and robotics are more likely to pursue STEM-related careers. In the context of Uzbekistan, introducing AI and robotics has the potential to modernize education and prepare students for the digital future.

However, the challenges identified in this study underscore the need for better infrastructure and teacher training. Ertmer & Ottenbreit-Leftwich [14] emphasize that without proper training, teachers may struggle to effectively deliver AI and robotics content, limiting students' learning potential.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The literature shows that teaching AI and robotics in high school offers significant benefits, including increased student engagement, improved problem-solving skills, and the development of computational thinking. Project-based learning, inquiry-based learning, and collaborative learning have been identified as effective teaching methods for these topics. However, challenges such as teacher training, resource availability, and integration into Informatics' education program must be addressed to fully realize the potential of AI and robotics education. As the demand for technological skills continues to grow, it is essential for schools to prepare students for the future by incorporating AI and robotics into their Informatics classes.

This research highlights the positive impact of teaching AI and robotics to high school students in Uzbekistan. The summer school program successfully increased student engagement, fostered problem-solving skills, and generated interest in STEM fields. However, for AI and robotics education to be sustainable and effective in Uzbekistan, further investments in resources, teacher training, and Informatics' education program development are required.

Based on this research and literature review we have summarized our recommendations for the further development of AI and Robotics education in high schools of Uzbekistan:

1. **Expand Access to AI and Robotics Tools:** Ministry of Preschool and School Education should invest in robotics kits, AI tools, and software to provide students with hands-on learning experiences.
2. **Teacher Training Programs:** Develop comprehensive training programs for ICT teachers to improve their knowledge of AI and robotics and enable them to deliver effective lessons.
3. **Integration of AI and robotics into Informatics' education program:** AI and robotics should be integrated into the existing Informatics' education program to ensure that all students have the opportunity to learn these essential skills.

4. Collaborative Projects: Encourage collaborative learning through group projects and competitions in AI and robotics to enhance students' creativity and teamwork abilities.

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